

PLURIDENTITIES

POLICY BRIEF 1

Work Package 3

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Problem statement

Rationale and policy problem

Across Europe, schools are expected to deliver two things at once: strong proficiency in the dominant school language(s) and meaningful opportunities to develop additional languages. At the same time, classrooms are becoming more linguistically diverse. This combination creates a clear policy challenge: multilingualism is widely valued in principle, but it is not consistently supported in practice. Too often, the languages pupils bring to school are treated as peripheral – something to manage, tolerate, or keep outside the classroom – rather than as potential resource for learning. Meanwhile, multilingual programmes can end up narrowing rather than widening pupils’ repertoires when they privilege one or two high-status additional language(s) (often including English) and leave little space for other languages that matter personally, socially, locally, or regionally.

Why policy does not automatically reach classrooms

A second problem is that language-in-education policy is rarely experienced as one coherent set of decisions. What is written at national level does not automatically become school practice; it is interpreted and reshaped across the macro (sub-/national), meso (providers and intermediaries such as regions, municipalities, boards and support networks) and micro (schools) layers, each with its own responsibilities and decision points. As a result, the same policy intentions can lead to different outcomes for pupils depending on local support structures, accountability pressures, and schools’ capacity (time, staffing, training). In some contexts, strong rules and inspection/testing steer schools toward compliance with the dominant language, which can (un)intentionally marginalise multilingual practices. In others, loose or non-binding regulation creates formal space, but without clear guidance that space can produce uneven provision, where opportunities depend heavily on the school a pupil attends rather than on context-sensitive decisions within a shared baseline. Importantly, policy also moves upward: school-level practices and constraints are channelled back through intermediary actors and can shape meso and macro adjustments over time. Taken together, the challenge for policymakers is to turn broad multilingual ambitions into coherent, workable and equitable school practice across diverse local contexts.

Research set-up

Document mapping across five contexts

This policy brief responds to that challenge by mapping language-in-education policy documents across five contexts (Spain, Sweden, Belgium, Aruba and the Netherlands) on three layers: macro, meso and micro. We mapped 67 documents across 5 contexts and 3 layers to locate decision points. Our analysis pays particular attention to the points where schools must make decisions that affect pupils directly: (1) the language(s) of instruction and how languages are allocated across subjects; (2) how language support is organised; and (3) whether pupils’

multilingual repertoires are recognised as learning resources, or only allowed in limited “safe” spaces (e.g., separate support lessons, newcomer provision, or informal settings outside classrooms).

The findings (see Table 1) are intended to support policymakers and intermediary actors in a practical way. The key contribution of this brief is to identify a small set of policy design levers that strengthen the macro–meso–micro chain. These levers enable supported autonomy – clear system-level guardrails combined with the capacity for schools to adapt to local needs – so multilingual ambitions become more implementable, consistent, and equitable. Across contexts, four levers repeatedly matter: coherence across levels (clear guidance from broad aims), capacity (staff, time, training, materials), intermediary support (boards / municipalities / networks translating policy into tools and professional learning), and aligned accountability (assessment and inspection that recognise multilingual practice rather than penalising it). In short, the aim is supported autonomy: a shared baseline (clarity, support, aligned incentives) that allows schools to tailor language policy to local needs while ensuring equitable opportunities for pupils. The country summaries below use the same lens to show where decisions sit across macro–meso–micro levels and where policymakers have the clearest leverage for action. We also highlight what this means for multilingualism in schools: mainstreamed, limited to add-ons, or confined to separate provisions (e.g., newcomer classes, mother-tongue support).

Results

Table 1 summarises where key decisions sit across macro rules, meso support and school practice, and where the policy chain tends to hold or break.

Table 1. When does language policy reach schools?

Context	Macro rules	Meso support	Conditions in practice	What happens in schools
Spain	Medium-high	Strong	Contestation & capacity constraints	Programmes/PLC (incl. CLIL); home languages marginal
Sweden	Medium	Variable	High accountability; staff gaps	Mother-tongue support separate; Swedish-dominant mainstream
Belgium (Flanders)	High	Strong	Testing/inspection steering	Multilingualism mostly separate provisions; informal tolerance
Aruba	Low-medium	Weak	High variation across schools	Uneven uptake; Dutch/English priority; remediation
Netherlands	Medium-low	Weak	Depends on school type	Mostly English/CLIL; migrant languages rarely included

In **Spain**, national language-in-education policy doesn’t simply *trickle down* from the state to schools. It gets filtered through the autonomous communities’ powers, and then it is turned into day-to-day practice through each school’s core planning documents, especially the *proyecto educativo* and the *proyecto lingüístico de centro* (PLC). What this means in practice is that

schools are constantly balancing different expectations at once: they need to respect state-wide minimum curriculum rules and broad legal principles, but they also must follow the language model set by their region, and then make it workable for their own pupil population and local context. The PLC is central because it pushes schools to translate abstract policy goals into concrete choices: how many hours are taught in which language, how languages are used across subjects, what counts as good practice in classrooms, and how progress is monitored. School autonomy is strongest when schools have room to tailor programmes locally (for example through bilingual/CLIL initiatives, local resources, and professional support), and when the PLC functions as a living, school-owned plan – used to coordinate staff, justify local adaptations, and make decisions transparent – rather than as a compliance document produced mainly for inspection. At the same time, autonomy is limited by political and legal disputes around language models in some regions, by assessment systems that can indirectly privilege certain languages, and by very practical constraints, staffing, timetabling, and whether teachers have the right qualifications, so that the options schools have *on paper* are not always feasible in practice.

In **Sweden**, national language-in-education policy is generally framed through goal-based steering: the state sets the overall aims, curricula and national assessment structures, but local authorities and schools have a lot of responsibility for deciding how those goals are reached. This creates real space for schools to shape their own language profile, whether that is a stronger English track, some form of CLIL, or more systematic support for *modersmål* ('mother tongue') teaching and study guidance. At school level, policy is *made real* through a series of everyday decisions that school leaders, teachers, and municipalities negotiate over time: how strictly Swedish should function as the default language across the school, when English is allowed to expand beyond the English subject, and how (or whether) pupils' home languages are treated as a learning resource in mainstream lessons. In other words, the same national policy text can lead to quite different outcomes depending on the school's demographics, leadership priorities, and local capacity. Autonomy is strengthened when schools can draw on local development projects, professional learning, and municipal support that legitimises multilingual approaches and gives teachers concrete tools. But it is constrained by accountability pressures (especially national tests and inspection priorities in Swedish and English), a persistent shortage of qualified staff for *modersmål* and study guidance, and organisational issues like scheduling that often pushes mother-tongue provision to the margins.

In **Belgium**, language-in-education policy is shaped by a combination of policy levels that is quite distinctive: schooling is organised around territorial language regimes tied to the three language communities (Dutch-, French- and German-speaking), with clear rules on the official language in each language area, while schools also operate in a system that grants them considerable autonomy in how they organise education. Schools therefore rarely get to renegotiate the official language of instruction, but they do shape many other parts of language policy in practice: how language expectations are communicated, how language learning is organised and monitored, how parents are engaged, and how additional language programmes (including selective CLIL options) are positioned in the school's offer. In Flanders, for example, Dutch is often framed in policy and public debate as central to participation, cohesion, and equal opportunity, and schools enact that through concrete routines: language rules in school regulations, targeted remediation trajectories, and strong steering via testing and inspection signals. Autonomy is enabled because schools are expected to develop an integrated language

policy and can draw on network structures and pedagogical guidance to design local plans that fit their pupil population. However, autonomy is also constrained by the territorial language regime, by the pressure to demonstrate measurable results in the dominant language, and by politicised debates about multilingualism and integration. This can make schools cautious about openly valuing pupils' home languages in formal policy, even when they sometimes pragmatically accommodate multilingual realities in informal spaces (corridors, playgrounds) or in specific support settings.

In **Aruba**, the *Departamento di Enseñansa* (Department of Education; DEA) is the national body that provides direction on language-in-education policy. Recently, national documents were written to stimulate multilingual trajectories and practices in education, while retaining a focus on the development of proficiency in Dutch. This stands out, as the home language of most Arubans is Papiamentu, not Dutch. Three potential trajectories for language use in education (Dutch-English bilingual education, Papiamentu-English bilingual education and Dutch as a foreign language-education) were proposed, as well as a continuous line in language development throughout formal education. However, DEA's policies are not binding for subsidized school boards and their schools in Aruba. School boards have significant freedoms in the way they provide education. Individual schools, in turn, also have significant freedoms, considering that the school boards have not developed their own language-in-education policies at present. While there is a turn towards multilingual approaches on the national level, school boards and schools have not adopted these on a large scale. As such, there are significant differences between schools in language-in-education practices, as well as between individual teachers. What all subsidized schools have in common is a conviction that proficiency in Dutch (as well as English) is important, with a view to higher education and labor opportunities abroad. As such, pupils from minoritized language backgrounds are frequently directed to remediation classes for Dutch and English.

In **the Netherlands**, language use in education is regulated by law, but the national framework is relatively broad and offers conditional flexibility rather than detailed, prescriptive guidance. The Secondary Education Act (*Wet op het voortgezet onderwijs*, WVO) includes specific provisions for Frisian in Fryslân, and more generally allows schools to use languages other than Dutch under certain conditions (e.g., linked to the structure of the programme or the background of the student body). In practice, Dutch remains the default language of instruction in mainstream schooling, and many actors do not translate this legal flexibility into an explicit, system-wide language policy. Instead, schools mainly make explicit policy choices when they adopt language provision beyond the Dutch default. For example, through international or bilingual/CLIL pathways, or through provision for newly arrived students. In these settings, schools are also more likely to articulate how (and whether) pupils' home languages can be used. Outside such contexts, regional and migrant languages receive little structural attention in mainstream schooling, with Frisian as a notable exception. Where migrant languages do feature, this is often primarily as a bridge to support the acquisition of Dutch (and sometimes English), rather than as a sustained educational resource in their own right.

Implications and takeaways

This document mapping shows where the macro–meso–micro policy chain holds – and where it weakens – in translating language-in-education ambitions into school practice. Where the meso layer provides usable guidance and schools have capacity (time, staffing, training), implementation is more coherent; where meso support is weak or non-binding, outcomes become uneven; and where macro steering is tightly tied to testing and inspection, priorities narrow to what is measured. This helps explain why multilingualism is often recognised in policy yet remains confined to separate provisions rather than mainstreamed as a routine classroom resource. The process is not one-way: school-level practices and constraints can also inform meso and macro adjustments when feedback channels exist. For policymakers, the main leverage is supported autonomy: a shared baseline plus room for local tailoring, enabled by (1) clear guardrails, (2) strong intermediary support, (3) sufficient school capacity, and (4) aligned accountability that recognises multilingual, inclusive practice.